

OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION (ORI) PROGRAM 2025-2030

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Versions

Version	Date	Author	Changes
D0.1	2024-02-25	Maurice Vanderfeesten	Initial draft
D0.5	2024-04-30	ORI team	Cleaned for public consultation
D0.6	2024-04-30	ORI Community	Added feedback, comments and enabled track changes
D0.9	2025-05-28	Maurice Vanderfeesten	Concise version with focus on vision, goals, and change strategy
F1.0	2025-07-04	Eileen Waegemaekers	Final version
F1.0.1	2025-08-28	Maurice Vanderfeesten	Added missing advisory board member

D =Draft; F = Final

Distribution

Version	Receiver	Required action (*)
D0.1	ORI team	For advice
D0.5	ORI community	For consultation
D0.6	ORI advisory board	For consultation
D0.9	ORI team	For decision
F1.0(.1)	ORI community	For information

*) For information, advice, consultation, decision

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1 ABOUT THIS DOCUMENT

The Open Research Information (ORI) program is part of the [SURF Innovation Zone Strengthening Open Science](#). The ambition of the ORI program was discussed and agreed upon in the SURF Members' Council of 13 December 2023. By doing so, they granted the coordinator of SURF's Innovation Zone Strengthen Open Science the mandate to draw up an ORI program.

The ambition is: 'All information about Dutch publicly funded research and its results are openly available and reusable.'

One of the activities that follow from this ambition is the development of an ORI program supported by the sector. The sector consists of the libraries of all Dutch research institutions, the UKB, VH, UNL, NFU, NWO, SIA, ZonMW, KNAW, CWTS and smaller research institutes. They are the stakeholders that benefit from the transition to open research information and those involved in implementation.

The ORI program builds on completed and ongoing projects that contribute to the ambition. The transition from closed to open research information is a complex transition in which SURF, through its innovation role, is committed to facilitating, coordinating and accelerating this transition, and jointly fulfilling the ambitions set out in the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#).

2 CONTEXT AND BACKGROUND

2.1 DEFINITION OF OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

By open research information we mean the descriptive metadata (including the persistent identifiers - PIDs), i.e. the contextual information about research and research output and (where possible) its enrichments, which is accessible and reusable without restrictions.

Put simply; freely accessible and reusable information describing who researched what, in which collaboration, with which funding and in which context, and what scientific and societal impact this achieved for whom.

2.2 DEPENDENCY ON CLOSED INFORMATION UNDERMINES ACADEMIC VALUES

The Open Research Information (ORI) program is a response to the growing reliance on commercial platforms to manage and use research information. This information is essential for assessing grant applications, evaluating research groups, strategic policies of institutions, and for recognising and rewarding researchers. It is also crucial for making research and results findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). This dependence on commercial parties and the closed nature of information and algorithms pose risks to the openness, accessibility, and transparency of research information. This undermines core [academic values](#) such as honesty, diligence, transparency, independence and accountability and increases the need for a robust national approach.

2.3 TRANSITION TO OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

The transition to open research information is essential to safeguard core academic values and scientific sovereignty, adhere to FAIR principles, and support both national and international policies, such as the [NPOS goals](#) and the aforementioned Barcelona Declaration. The demise of [NARCIS](#) has further increased the urgency for a national approach. Guidelines such as the ["Seven Guiding Principles for Open Research Information"](#) and the ["Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure \(POSI\)"](#) have been drafted in view of new negotiations with major data brokers such as Elsevier, Clarivate and Digital Science, and provide institutions with guidance in the transition to open research information.

2.4 ALIGNMENT WITH NATIONAL AMBITION

In the national open science context, the ORI program and SURF's role in it is located within the 'Open Infrastructures' pillar of the [NPOS Ambition Document 2030 and its Rolling Agenda](#) (see Figure 1). This program aims to respond to the need for national coordination (page 17), specifically in the area of open research information. It aligns with the NPOS Strategic Goal 'Towards Open Scholarly Communication' (page 24) and is strongly reflected in Objective 3.2, which describes a platform for open publications and metadata (page 25). and in Section 'Towards FAIR and Open Research Outputs' (page 25) the objectives 4.1 and 4.3 arguing for standardising open meta-information on FAIR research outputs.

Figure 1 NPOS. (2022). Open Science 2030 in the Netherlands: NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda (Approved version). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433767> with addition highlighting the role of SURF to nationally coordinate open infrastructures for open science, and for this program a focus on Open Scholarly Communication.

The program is also in line with the ambitions described in the [Open Science NL work program](#) in the Open Infrastructures cluster, specifically the need for a platform for open metadata is highlighted (page 17). [UNL's Open Science Agenda](#) mentions the focal areas 'a federated network of repositories' (focal area 1; page 6) and 'a central warehouse for (enriched) open metadata' (focal area 2; page 7). Finally, the universities of applied sciences are also committed to open research information, including through the new platform Publinova and attention to this topic in various working groups of the [DCC-PO](#).

2.5 DIGITAL COMMONS AND INTERNATIONAL INITIATIVES

The program aims to develop a "digital commons", in which research information is considered a public community asset under public governance. The [Global Open Research Commons \(GORC\)](#) provides a model for establishing such a commons considering 9 elements; Governance Structures; Rules of Participation & Access; Engagement; Human Capacity; Sustainability; Interoperability & Standards; Compute, Storage, Network & AAI; Services & Tools; and Research Objects.

There are several international initiatives that relate to the ambition of the ORI program. As mentioned above, the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) is an important initiative that was launched specifically to encourage the transition to openness of research information. There are also parallels with the [EOSC](#) initiative, in which federation of research information is a part.

3 AMBITION AND VISION

The ambition for the ORI program is described in the plan submitted to the SURF Members' Council for the 'Innovation Zone: Strengthening Open Science' (part of the SURF strategy 2022 - 2027). This ambition has been translated into a compelling vision.

To achieve this, we are building a digital, federated ecosystem of open research information. This ecosystem supports the core academic values - honesty, diligence, transparency, independence and accountability - by returning control of research information to public institutions. In this way, we ensure that science can operate based on public values and that the knowledge landscape remains accessible and reliable for society as a whole.

This ecosystem supports researchers and institutions in their open science ambitions and creates an infrastructure that is interoperable, sustainable and inclusive. The bigger dream behind this program is to realise an environment where research information is freely accessible and can be used without restrictions to increase the visibility and impact of research.

3.1 NEW OPPORTUNITIES

Besides facilitating Open Science goals, this ecosystem enables a wide range of opportunities. When the infrastructure and governance of research information are in place, new applications can be developed that go beyond open access. Examples include:

- **Advanced analysis and monitoring:** With reliable and standardised metadata, researchers, policymakers and institutions can conduct more in-depth analyses, for example to identify trends in research output or map collaborations between researchers.
- **More efficient collaboration and matchmaking:** Researchers can more easily find colleagues based on shared areas of expertise or research projects, promoting interdisciplinary research and innovative collaborations.
- **Impact measurement and reporting:** Using persistent identifiers and standardised metadata, the impact of research can be measured and reported more accurately. This is important for institutions, funders and policymakers to substantiate the value of publicly funded research.
- **Supporting education and innovation:** Open access to rich research information provides opportunities for information reuse in educational contexts and in innovation processes at public and private organisations.
- **Strengthening digital sovereignty:** By managing a national infrastructure for research information, the Netherlands retains control over its research information, reduces dependence on commercial parties and ensures control over how this information is shared and used.

Through these applications, mentioned in ORIA open research information agenda (UNL, 2022) and Customized Research Evaluation (Bosman & Kramer, 2024), the ORI program can contribute to a transparent, collaborative and innovation-oriented research ecosystem that not only meets Open Science ambitions, but also contributes to broader societal and economic goals.

4 GOALS

In this chapter we describe the strategic goals which help provide direction to our mission and vision.

4.1 STRATEGIC GOALS

The strategic goals for the information chain are inspired by the approach of the National Digital Heritage Strategy. (Erfgoed & Ministry of Education, 2021), the Open Research Information Agenda (UNL, 2022), and following recommendations from the study "Coverage and quality of open metadata for Dutch research output" (Kramer, 2024), which is in line with the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information.

4.1.1 STRONGER FOUNDATION FOR OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

In this program line, we aim for greater consistency and clearer agreements on the adoption of persistent identifiers (PIDs) and the exchange of metadata. This will allow research information to be aggregated automatically across institutional boundaries, enabling meaningful reuse of this information. Using PIDs also ensures sustainable accessibility and allows for more advanced analysis further down the information chain.

OUR AIM:

- Transparent Domain architecture of the players and information flows in the information chain
- Clearer agreements on roles and responsibilities between the players for research information exchange
- Increased adoption of Persistent Identifiers for research entities (e.g. researchers, output, projects, instruments)
- Clarity about licensing and (re)use of metadata in the information chain
- Data model for research information exchange in various research processes based on CERIF

The feasibility study "[a Dutch Open Knowledge Base](#)" (Kemman & Te Velde, 2020), the "[Seven Guiding Principles for open Research Information](#)" (Bijsterbosch et al., 2022), the reports "[Towards a national PID roadmap](#)" (Akcaova et al., 2022) and "[Coverage and quality of open metadata for Dutch research output—Report](#)" (Bianca Kramer, 2024) show that these are the boundary conditions that enable us to develop a federated and open ecosystem for research information.

4.1.2 HIGHER QUALITY AND COVERAGE OF METADATA IN MORE DIVERSE RESEARCH PROCESSES

In this program line we want to improve how we cover various research processes with high quality metadata. Currently, the focus of metadata describing research processes is on the publishing and deposit process. This implies that metadata only covers output and information about research will only be shared at the end of a research project, not during. To improve transparency of the entire research process, we need information in the processes of grant applications, data management, ethical reviews, pre-registration etc.. The information in these processes is not covered and lack standardization.

OUR AIM:

- More non-traditional research output (gray literature, policy briefs, etc.) have a PID and are covered in the total Dutch research production
- Better agreements on metadata schemas to describe information in other processes than publishing
- Higher quality of the metadata based on the above metadata schemas

4.1.3 DEEPER CONNECTIONS AND ENRICHMENTS

In this program line we want to federatively aggregate the information to connect and enrich individual records based on the collective input. Currently, there are incomplete records that lack several metadata fields and PIDs to other connected research entities. Because of these incomplete records it becomes difficult to do advanced analyses that go beyond the institutional level. To improve the interconnectedness of research entities and make advanced analyses possible, we need to aggregate the information and send back the enriched records to the source systems.

OUR AIM:

- More institutions use the enriched records from open infrastructures at the national and international level
- Easier to obtain high quality records for advanced reporting
- Better information about the provenance of the source of the enriched records.

The feasibility study "a Dutch Open Knowledge Base" (Kemman & Te Velde, 2020) shows that it is desirable and feasible to federatively aggregate and provide enriched feedback to the source systems. This is also a desirable development according to focal areas 1 (Federative network of repositories) and 2 (Central hub for research information) of the "UNL Open Science Agenda" (UNL - Association of universities in the Netherlands, 2023). Also the recommendation from Kramer2024) is to extent to the use open research information sources to fill or enrich CRIS systems.

4.1.4 BETTER VISIBILITY, USABILITY, AND SUSTAINABILITY OF OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

In this program line we ensure that the connected and enriched research information is accessible and reusable for the end-user. Both (Faniel et al., 2024) and (Kramer, 2024) show that research information that lives in repositories and CRIS's in research organisations does not end up where the user is. End-users, therefore, may get an incomplete view of the state of research in the Netherlands. Also, there is no clear strategy to archive research information for the long term. To improve the visibility, usability and sustainability of the research information for the end-user, research organisations need to ensure that the information is made available to open metadata outlets as soon as possible.

OUR AIM:

- Enriched and connected research information is made available to open infrastructures at the national and international level
- Dutch Open research information is stored in a reusable format and archived for the long term.

5 CHANGE STRATEGY / THEORY OF CHANGE

The change strategy in this program is built on two key pillars: monitoring and communicating. As a collaborative network of Dutch higher education and research institutions, SURF operates without a strong directive mandate. Instead, we rely on a shared vision, influence, and soft power to drive transformation. Change is rooted in the intrinsic motivation of institutions to work toward a common, higher purpose. Achieving this requires bold objectives with clearly defined key results and making the change visible through progress tracking and communication. By combining monitoring with communication, we enable playful leaderboard competitions between the institutions. While institutions are the true agents of change, SURF's role is to facilitate: to coordinate, observe, visualize progress, and inspire action.

5.1 MONITORING AND STEERING

At the start of each year (January), we develop a work plan in which we specify the projects we will work on and how they contribute to the strategic goals. The work plan gives a project-centric view of the ORI activities that we will use alongside the OKR (Objective and Key Results) framework for monitoring progress.

The OKR framework is used to set objectives, and measurable key results and fits an agile way of working. We match the OKR cycles to the trimestral (4-month periods) reporting cycles of SURF (M4, M8, M12). Based on the strategic goals and aims, defined in previous chapter, we refine them into objectives and a maximum of three measurable key results that we aim to achieve in a 4-month period. These OKRs are our program's focus for that period and the key results are put onto a dashboard that is publicly visible to the ORI community.

For each 4-month period, we first draft the objectives and key results with our program team. Together with the advisory board, we refine and formalize them.

5.2 COMMUNICATION

The purpose of communication is to establish and maintain an active ORI community, keeping it informed and engaged and, where necessary, prompting action.

We identify four groups:

1. The IZOS Steering group;
2. The ORI advisory group;
3. The ORI community (consisting of groups such as the RINN, WISH, PURE user group NL, UKB-RS, etc.);
4. The broader Open Science community

The program is supported by SURF's communication advisor: Dorien Brugmans.

Communication resources:

1. **The SURF ORI community event calendar:** The community and the ORI team provide an up-to-date calendar of all meetings relevant to the ORI community, including meetings of the ORCID consortium, the PURE user group, RINN, WISH and the OpenAIRE community calls. The calendar also includes international events such as PIDfest and events organised by the Barcelona Declaration.
2. **The SURF ORI community blog:** The community and the ORI team publish relevant blog posts, such as reports of important meetings and announcements or results of interventions that have brought the program closer to achieving its goals.
3. **ORI lecture:** A monthly (hybrid) lecture where a colleague from the field presents their project, intervention plan or outcomes. The aim is to inspire other institutions and demonstrate the various activities related to the program. This could be incorporated into the SURF Shorts/SURF Sounds podcast format.

6 PROGRAM ORGANISATION

The program is part of the SURF Innovation Zone Strengthening Open Science (IZ-OS).

Within the IZ-OS there are three programs; FAIR data, Open Research Information, and Open Scholarly Communication. This innovation zone and its programs aim for the responsible handling of research information and control over the sharing, finding and evaluation of publicly funded research. The IZ-OS is mandated by the SURF membership council. The ORI program is represented in the *regiegroep Innovation Zone Open Science* by the chair of the advisory board.

6.1 PROGRAM BOARD

The program board is the highest level of management inside the program. The board has ultimate responsibility for the program and delegates its daily management to the program manager while they keep an eye on the manager through program assurance, as explained in the chapter about theory of change.

Role	Who	Responsibilities
Program executive	Laurents Sesink (SURF)	Is responsible of the Strategic alignment of the program with SURF strategic goals of the Innovation zone Open Science.
Senior User	Darco Jansen (UNL)	Represents the ORI user community in the Regiegroep Innovation Zone Open Science, and keeps a connection with the Chiefs Open Science in the Netherlands and their strategic agenda.
Senior Supplier	John Doove (SURF)	Is responsible for the resources for program execution.
Program manager	Eileen Waegemaekers (SURF)	Has the authority to run the program on behalf of the Program board. Is responsible for the day-to-day execution of the program, and achieving deliverables, and reports to the Program board.

6.2 ADVISORY BOARD

The ORI Program manager is accountable to the advisory group. The chairman of this advisory group is represented in the Innovation Zone Open Science (Regiegroep IZ-OS) for liaison with the other programmes within this zone. In this version of the program plan, the advisory group consists of the following members:

Organisation	Represents (stakeholder group)	Who	Role
UNL	Dutch Universities	Darco Jansen	Chair
UKB	Universiteitsbibliotheken en Koninklijke bibliotheek	Arjan Schalken	Member
DCC-PO	Hogescholen / Dutch Universities of Applied Science	Sarah Coombs	Member
AUMC / NFU	Dutch Academic Hospitals	Lieuwe Kool	Member
UL / CWTS	Bibliometrics, Scientometrics, Research Intelligence	Nees Jan van Eck	Member
EUR / RINN	Research Intelligence Network Netherlands	Rik Iping	Member
NWO / OS-NL	Dutch Research Funders / Open Science NL	Jeroen Sondervan	Member
DANS / OSC	Dutch Open Science Community	Loek Brinkman	Member

HANZE	Dutch PURE User group	Annemieke Brands	Member
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6.3 PROGRAM TEAM MEMBERS

The program team is a small core unit that is responsible for the coordinated management and delivery of the program. Rather than directing change, the team enables it—by involving the ORI community in translating strategic goals into achievable steps, making progress visible through transparent monitoring, and fostering a shared sense of purpose among institutions. Through collaboration, communication, and soft power, the team supports the community-led transition to open research information.

Role	Who	Responsibilities
Program manager	Eileen Waegemaekers (SURF)	Is responsible for the day-to-day execution of the program, and achieving deliverables.
Program advisor	Maurice Vanderfeesten (VU/SURF)	Is responsible for the strategic advice on achieving open research information.
Information architect	Till Bey (SURF)	Is responsible for the information architecture, overview of the federated ecosystem and information exchange standards.
Project support	Claudia Visser (SURF)	Is responsible for the community and facility management
Project manager	Karin van Grieken (SURF)	Is responsible for operational project management.
Information specialist	Rutger de Jong (ULeiden/SURF)	Is responsible for statistics on research information, and support for CRIS and repository managers for compliancy to research information standards.
Domain Architect	Maarten Hoogerwerf (SURF)	Is responsible for aligning the ORI activities with the research domain (within innovation)
<i>Ad hoc team members:</i>		
Technical product manager	Peter Dubbeld (SURF)	Is responsible for PID implementation in Publinova
Technical Advisor	Menno Grijpma (SURF)	Is responsible for technical alignment of UKBsis to ORI

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